

Synthesis, and biological evaluation of novel 2-(3-(5-cyano-6-oxo-4-phenyl-1,6-dihydropyridin-2-yl)phenoxy)acetic acid as potential in vivo anti-inflammatory agent

Alshimaa Kh. M. Ahmed^{1,2}, Mamdouh F. A. Mohamed^{2,*}, Eman A. M. Beshr^{1,2,*},

¹ Department of Medicinal Chemistry, Faculty of Pharmacy, Minia University, Minia 61519, Egypt.

² Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Faculty of Pharmacy, Sohag University, 82524 Sohag, Egypt.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14974196>

Published Date: 05-March-2025

Abstract: Novel target compound, 2-(3-(5-cyano-6-oxo-4-phenyl-1,6-dihydropyridin-2-yl)phenoxy)acetic acid **2**, was synthesized and evaluated for its anti-inflammatory activity using carrageenan-induced rat paw edema method in comparison with the selective COX-2 inhibitor, celecoxib. The results suggested that compound **2** proved good potency with edema inhibition rates of 22.28 and 25.23% at the third and fifth hours, respectively. More SAR study and optimization are warranted for compound **2**, which has the potential to be employed as oral anti-inflammatory drugs.

Keywords: Cyanopyridine; Anti-inflammatory; COX; Cyclooxygenase enzymes; Selective COX-2.

1. INTRODUCTION

Inflammation is a complex physiological response of the immune system against any foreign stimuli or irritants. Immune cells, such as neutrophils, macrophages, and lymphocytes, are activated and recruited and then they release different pro-inflammatory mediators.^[1, 2] For example, activated macrophages can stimulate the production of tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α), nitric oxide (NO), and pro-inflammatory cytokines, including interleukin-6 (IL-6) and interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β), among others.^[3, 4] This series of events is beneficial in regulating tissue homeostasis, regeneration, repair, and remodeling.^[5] When inflammation persists, it can cause cell injury, tissue destruction, and organ dysfunction. This can cause chronic inflammatory conditions, including osteoporosis, Alzheimer's disease, colitis, rheumatic fever, septic shock, atherosclerosis, asthma, rheumatoid arthritis, inflammatory bowel syndrome, and some types of cancer.^[2, 5, 6]

Aspirin, ibuprofen, naproxen, and indomethacin (**Figure 1**) are examples of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs that are useful in treating inflammatory symptoms, such as fever, pain, and both acute and chronic inflammations.^[7-9] NSAIDs have analgesic, anti-inflammatory, and antipyretic properties due to their ability to inhibit the cyclooxygenase (COX) enzymes (COX-1) and COX-2, which are involved in the manufacture of prostaglandins.^[10] There are two main types of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs): the more modern, selective COX-2 inhibitors that mainly inhibit COX-2 and the older, conventional, non-selective NSAIDs that inhibit both COX-1 and COX-2.^[7, 11] Prolonged clinical use of non-selective NSAIDs can lead to a number of adverse effects, including renal damage, ulceration, bleeding, and gastrointestinal irritation because they inhibit COX-1's ability to produce gastro-protective prostanoids in the gastrointestinal tract.^[12, 13] Selective COX-2 inhibitors like celecoxib can help lessen side effects related to the gastrointestinal tract.^[14, 15]

Fig. 1. Examples of NSAIDs: (I) aspirin (II) Indomethacin (III) ibuprofen (IV) celecoxib

In drug design and biochemistry, carboxylic acids and their bioisosteres have highly versatile functionality. Carboxylic moiety is present in numerous endogenous compounds, including prostanoids, triglycerides, fatty acids, DNA, RNA, and amino acids.^[16] Since they can form electrostatic interactions with different proteins, carboxylic acids are frequently referred to as privileged structures for building therapeutic agents. In 2010, about 450 commercialized drugs containing carboxylic residue in their structure were marketed globally, including NSAIDs, antibiotics, anticoagulants, and statins, among others.^[17-20] Carboxylic acids dissociate to carboxylate ions at pH 7.4, which increases their water solubility and ability to form hydrogen bonds and dipole interactions.^[21] Due to their acidity, pKa value of 5, and planar geometry, they comply with optimal physicochemical and bioavailability standards.^[22, 23]

Pyridine moiety is a highly significant class in both organic and medicinal chemistry, it serves as the essential structural basis for almost 7000 known drugs and also has tremendous applications in medicinal chemistry^[24-29]. Fused cyanopyridines, especially 3-cyano-2-pyridones, possess a variety of pharmacological and biological activities, including antioxidant^[30, 31], sedatives^[32], analgesic^[33], antiviral^[34], anticonvulsant^[35], antibiotic^[36-38], antidepressant^[39], anti-inflammatory^[33, 40, 41], antimicrobial^[42-47], cardiotoxic^[48, 49], and anticancer activity^[44, 50-54].

The nucleus of 2-oxo-3-cyanopyridine (V) bears similarities to that of ricinine (VI), the first alkaloid with a cyano group that is known to exist. Milrinone (VII) (Figure 2), an inhibitor of dipyridinephosphodiesterase, is a non-glycosidic cardiotoxic drug. Its synthesis and investigation underscored the significance of 2-oxo-3-cyanopyridine as a pharmacologically and physiologically active prospective chemical^[55]. Olprinone (VIII), is also an inhibitor of phosphodiesterase III, which has both vasodilator and positive inotropic effects^[56]. In 2023, a novel series of 2-oxo-3-cyanopyridine derivatives was synthesized as dual EGFR/BRAF^{V600E} inhibitors. **Compound IX**, showed the highest antiproliferative activity against Panc-1 cancer (IC₅₀ = 0.80 μM) surpassing doxorubicin (IC₅₀ = 1.00 μM). Similar to erlotinib (IC₅₀ = 60 nM and 80 nM), **compound IX** exhibits comparable suppression of EGFR and BRAF^{V600E} (IC₅₀ = 89 nM and 65 nM)^[57].

Fig. 2. General structure of 2-oxo-3-cyanopyridine(V), and examples of biologically important cyanopyridine derivatives: ricinine (VI), Milrinone (VII), Olprinone (VIII), 2-oxo-3-cyanopyridine derivative as EGFR/BRAF inhibitor (IX).

There is a pressing need for developing therapeutic agents that fulfill the pharmacophoric standards of anti-inflammatory drugs without causing any of their side effects. In this research, hybrids of 2-oxo-3-cyanopyridines and carboxyl moiety were synthesized to create promising anti-inflammatory agents. Target compound, 2-(3-(5-cyano-6-oxo-4-phenyl-1,6-dihydropyridin-2-yl)phenoxy)acetic acid **2** was synthesized and tested for their *in vivo* anti-inflammatory activity *via* carrageenan-induced rat paw edema in comparison with the selective COX-2 inhibitor, celecoxib.

2. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

2.1 Chemistry

Cyanopyridine derivatives are considered a rich moiety that possesses various applications in medicinal chemistry^[58-61]. There are several known synthetic processes for producing 3-cyano-2-oxa-4-substituted pyridines, such as condensation of chalcones with ethyl cyanoacetate and excess ammonium acetate in ethanol under refluxing conditions^[62-66], *via* a one-pot, four-component reaction with substituted acetophenone, ethyl cyanoacetate or malonitrile, suitable aldehyde, and an excess of ammonium acetate, either without using a solvent or *via* using a variety of solvents, such as ethanol, toluene, and butanol^[49, 67-71]. Utilizing a catalytic quantity of piperidine with an activated nitrile, suitable aldehyde in ethanol^[72-75], or by stirring for 15 minutes while refluxing equimolar amounts of the relevant -dicarbonyl chemical with malonitrile and triethylamine in ethanol^[76, 77].

Target compound **2**, was synthesized, as shown in Scheme 1, *via* a single-pot reaction of (3-acetylphenoxy) acetic acid **1**, *p*-nitro benzaldehyde, excess ammonium acetate, and ethyl cyanoacetate in refluxing conditions in ethanol for 22 hours to yield 2-(3-(5-cyano-6-oxo-4-phenyl-1,6-dihydropyridin-2-yl)phenoxy)acetic acid **2** in 92.5% yield ranging. The proposed structure has been validated by spectroscopic and elemental analysis.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of 2-(3-(5-cyano-6-oxo-4-phenyl-1,6-dihydropyridin-2-yl)phenoxy)acetic acid **2**.

Reagents and conditions: (i) K_2CO_3 , DMF, reflux, 9 h, then HCl; (ii) *p*-nitro benzaldehyde, ethyl cyanoacetate, ammonium acetate, EtOH, reflux, 22 h; (ii) acetophenone, ethyl cyanoacetate, ammonium acetate, EtOH, reflux, 22 h.

3. PHARMACOLOGICAL SCREENING

3.1 *In vivo* investigation of the anti-inflammatory activity (Carrageenan-induced Acute Inflammatory Model).

The results in **Table 1** showed that compound **2** at the third and fifth hours exhibited a good anti-inflammatory efficacy compared to celecoxib-treated group, Consequently, the anti-inflammatory properties of compound **2** seems to be promising.

Table 1: *In vivo* anti-inflammatory effect of tested compound **2** and celecoxib as reference drug.

Treatment	Diameter inflammation (mm)				% Edema inhibition			
	0h	1h	3h	5h	0h	1h	3h	5h
Control	3.83±0.2	3.83±0.2	3.83±0.2	3.83±0.2	-----	-----	-----	-----
Carrageenan	6.1±0.1	7.06±0.05	7.63±0.20	8.52±0.37	-----	-----	-----	-----
Celecoxib	6.13±0.15	5.16±0.15	4.9±0.1	5.1±0.1	0.00	26.90	35.77	40.14
2	5.1±0.1	6.4±0.65	5.93±0.97	6.13±0.77	16.39	9.34	22.28	25.23

Values are displayed as mean \pm S.D. (n=6). The % of inflammation inhibition was calculated according to the following equation % inhibition = $(WC-WT/WC) \times 100$, where WC is the increase in paw thickness of the control group while WT is the increase in paw thickness of treated rats with test compounds.

4. CONCLUSION

To sum up, a novel cyanopyridine compound **2** was synthesized and screened for its *in vivo* anti-inflammatory activity using carrageenan-induced rat paw edema, using the selective COX-2 inhibitor, celecoxib as reference drug. The results proved that compound **2** displayed a good antiinflammatory activity and can be useful in treatment of inflammations. More SAR study and optimization are warranted for compound **2**, which has the potential to be employed as oral anti-inflammatory drugs.

5. EXPERIMENTAL

5.1 Chemistry

The melting points were ascertained using the Stuart electro-thermal melting point instrument, with uncorrected findings. Infrared spectra are obtained on KBr disks using a Shimaduz 408 instrument spectrophotometer at Sohag University's Faculty of Science. Using TMS as the internal reference, JEOL JNM-ECA400 (^1H : 400 MHz, ^{13}C : 100 MHz) NMR spectra were examined. Coupling constants (J) in Hertz and chemical shifts (δ) in ppm were reported relative to the remaining deuterated solvent DMSO- d_6 (2.5 for proton and 39.50 for carbon). Elemental analysis was within $\pm 0.4\%$ of the theoretical values, according to the Regional Center for Mycology and Biotechnology at Al-Azhar University in Cairo, Egypt. The development of the reactions was observed using pre-coated TLC plates (Kieselgel 60 F254, Merck).

5.1.1 General procedure for the synthesis of 2-(3-(5-cyano-6-oxo-4-phenyl-1,6-dihydropyridin-2-yl)phenoxy)acetic acid **2**.

To a vigorously stirred suspension of 2-(3-acetylphenoxy)acetic acid **1** (1.94 g, 10 mmol), 4-nitrobenzaldehyde (10 mmol), ethyl cyanoacetate (1.131 g, 10 mmol), and excess ammonium acetate (6.2 g, 80 mmol) using ethanol as a solvent (50 mL). the reaction mixture was heated under reflux for 22 hours. At the end of the reaction (TLC monitoring), The precipitate was filtered, washed with cold water, dried, and recrystallized from ethanol to yield 2-(3-(5-cyano-6-oxo-4-phenyl-1,6-dihydropyridin-2-yl)phenoxy)acetic acid **2** as yellow powder; yield (1.6 g, 92.5%); mp 333-335 °C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): $\tilde{\nu}$ 3668 (NH), 3118 (O=C-OH), 3084 (CH-Pyridine), 2912 (CH₂), 2219 (CN), 1712 (O=C-OH), 1623 (C=O-pyridine), 1230 (C-O); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ (ppm): 12.89 (s, 2H, OH, NH), 7.73 (dd, 2H, $J = 8, 4$ Hz, HC-C-CH), 7.60 – 7.54 (m, 3H), 7.51 (d, 1H, $J = 8$ Hz, CH-CH=CH), 7.46 (t, 1H, $J = 8$ Hz, CH-CH=CH), 7.42 (d, 1H, $J = 8$ Hz, CH-CH=CH), 7.12 (dd, 1H, $J = 8, 4$ Hz, OC-CH-CH=CH), 6.87 (s, 1H, pyridine-CH), 4.81 (s, 2H, CH₂); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ (ppm): 170.32, 162.22, 160.13, 158.23, 151.12, 136.18, 133.59, 130.66, 130.40, 129.01, 128.42, 120.77, 118.27, 116.69, 113.19, 106.51, 98.82, 64.91; Anal. Calcd. For C₂₀H₁₄N₂O₄ (346.34): C, 69.36; H, 4.07; N, 8.09, Found: C, 69.54; H, 4.23; N, 8.27.

5.2 Biological Evaluation

5.2.1 *In vivo* anti-inflammatory activity

For *in vivo* anti-inflammatory activity investigation, We utilized 200 g weighing male Wister rats.

The test was carried out in compliance with the laboratory animal care criteria established by the Institutional Animals Ethics Committee (IAEC). For the *in vivo* assessment of the anti-inflammatory activity using the carrageenan induced paw oedema model of the novel compound **2**, celecoxib was used as the reference medication. We used nine groups of rats: Rats from groups 1 and 2 administered the vehicle. Rats in group three were given a 50 mg/kg dosage of celecoxib. Rat group 4 was receiving our synthetic compound **2**, respectively. Thirty minutes prior to the injection of carrageenan, the tested compound was injected with dose of 50 mg/kg. Before tested compound was administered to the rats orally, it was dissolved in recently made carboxymethyl cellulose CMC (0.5%). A subplanter injection of 100 μL of freshly made 1% carrageenan soln in distilled water was used to form changes in the thickness of each rat's left hind paw (percentage of edema inhibition) [78]. The thickness of the paws was measured using a Vernier caliper following injections of carrageenan at 1, 3, and 5 hours. GraphPad Prism (version 9) was used to process the acquired data, which were then presented as mean \pm SD. Using a one-way ANOVA and the Tukey-Kramer test to assess the significance of the mean difference, values with $p < 0.05$ were deemed significant [79].

REFERENCES

- [1] Ma, L., et al., Structural exploration, synthesis and pharmacological evaluation of novel 5-benzylidenethiazolidine-2, 4-dione derivatives as iNOS inhibitors against inflammatory diseases. 2015. 92: p. 178-190.
- [2] Medzhitov, R.J.C., Inflammation 2010: new adventures of an old flame. 2010. 140(6): p. 771-776.
- [3] Zhang, J.-M. and J.J.I.a.c. An, Cytokines, inflammation and pain. 2007. 45(2): p. 27.
- [4] Kobayashi, Y.J.J.o.l.b., The regulatory role of nitric oxide in proinflammatory cytokine expression during the induction and resolution of inflammation. 2010. 88(6): p. 1157-1162.
- [5] Medzhitov, R.J.N., Origin and physiological roles of inflammation. 2008. 454(7203): p. 428-435.
- [6] Mantovani, A., et al., Cancer-related inflammation. 2008. 454(7203): p. 436-444.
- [7] Day, R.O. and G.G.J.B. Graham, Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs). 2013. 346.
- [8] Sng, B.L. and S.A.J.A.A.M.S. Schug, The role of opioids in managing chronic non-cancer pain. 2009. 38(11): p. 960-966.
- [9] Eccles, R.J.J.o.C.P. and Therapeutics, Efficacy and safety of over-the-counter analgesics in the treatment of common cold and flu. 2006. 31(4): p. 309-319.
- [10] Fu, J.-Y., et al., The induction and suppression of prostaglandin H2 synthase (cyclooxygenase) in human monocytes. 1990. 265(28): p. 16737-16740.
- [11] Kurumbail, R.G., et al., Structural basis for selective inhibition of cyclooxygenase-2 by anti-inflammatory agents. 1996. 384(6610): p. 644-648.
- [12] Abdel-Aziz, M., et al., New nitric oxide donating 1, 2, 4-triazole/oxime hybrids: synthesis, investigation of anti-inflammatory, ulcerogenic liability and antiproliferative activities. 2013. 21(13): p. 3839-3849.
- [13] Sun, X.-Y., et al., Synthesis and anti-inflammatory activity evaluation of some novel 6-alkoxy (phenoxy)-[1, 2, 4] triazolo [3, 4-a] phthalazine-3-amine derivatives. 2010. 45(11): p. 4807-4812.
- [14] Masferrer, J.L., et al., Selective inhibition of inducible cyclooxygenase 2 in vivo is antiinflammatory and nonulcerogenic. 1994. 91(8): p. 3228-3232.
- [15] Redasani, V.K. and S.B.J.E.j.o.m.c. Bari, Synthesis and evaluation of mutual prodrugs of ibuprofen with menthol, thymol and eugenol. 2012. 56: p. 134-138.
- [16] Hajduk, P.J., et al., Privileged molecules for protein binding identified from NMR-based screening. 2000. 43(18): p. 3443-3447.
- [17] Böcker, A., et al., Development of Specific "Drug-Like Property" Rules for Carboxylate-Containing Oral Drug Candidates. 2010. 5(12): p. 2102-2113.
- [18] Ballatore, C., D.M. Huryn, and A.B.J.C. Smith III, Carboxylic acid (bio) isosteres in drug design. 2013. 8(3): p. 385-395.
- [19] Youssif, B.G., et al., Novel aryl carboximidamide and 3-aryl-1, 2, 4-oxadiazole analogues of naproxen as dual selective COX-2/15-LOX inhibitors: Design, synthesis and docking studies. 2019. 85: p. 577-584.
- [20] Kalgutkar, A.S., J.S.J.M. Daniels, Pharmacokinetics, and T.o.F.G.I.o.C.B.B.o. ADMET, Carboxylic acids and their bioisosteres. 2010: p. 99-167.
- [21] David, S., et al., Impact of the counterion on the solubility and physicochemical properties of salts of carboxylic acid drugs. 2012. 38(1): p. 93-103.
- [22] Lipinski, C.A., et al., Experimental and computational approaches to estimate solubility and permeability in drug discovery and development settings. 2012. 64: p. 4-17.

International Journal of Novel Research in Life Sciences

 Vol. 12, Issue 2, pp: (1-8), Month: March - April 2025, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

- [23] Congreve, M., et al., A 'rule of three' for fragment-based lead discovery? 2003. 8(19): p. 876-877.
- [24] Li, A.-H., et al., Synthesis, CoMFA analysis, and receptor docking of 3, 5-diacyl-2, 4-dialkylpyridine derivatives as selective A₃ adenosine receptor antagonists. *Journal of medicinal chemistry*, 1999. 42(4): p. 706-721.
- [25] Vacher, B., et al., Novel derivatives of 2-pyridinemethylamine as selective, potent, and orally active agonists at 5-HT_{1A} receptors. *Journal of medicinal chemistry*, 1999. 42(9): p. 1648-1660.
- [26] Murata, T., et al., Characterization of phosphodiesterase 3 in human malignant melanoma cell line. *Anticancer research*, 2002. 22(6A): p. 3171-3174.
- [27] Teague, S.J., Synthesis of heavily substituted 2-aminopyridines by displacement of a 6-methylsulfinyl group. *The Journal of Organic Chemistry*, 2008. 73(24): p. 9765-9766.
- [28] Wells, J.A. and C.L.J.N. McClendon, Reaching for high-hanging fruit in drug discovery at protein-protein interfaces. 2007. 450(7172): p. 1001-1009.
- [29] Li, A.-H., et al., Synthesis, CoMFA analysis, and receptor docking of 3, 5-diacyl-2, 4-dialkylpyridine derivatives as selective A₃ adenosine receptor antagonists. 1999. 42(4): p. 706-721.
- [30] Sayed, H.H., E.M. Morsy, and E.M.J.S.C. Fiefel, Synthesis and reactions of some novel nicotinonitrile, thiazolotriazole, and imidazolotriazole derivatives for antioxidant evaluation. 2010. 40(9): p. 1360-1370.
- [31] Kotb, E.R., et al., A concise synthesis and antimicrobial activity of a novel series of naphthylpyridine-3-carbonitrile compounds. 2013. 70(4): p. 667-679.
- [32] Collins, I., et al., 3-Heteroaryl-2-pyridones: Benzodiazepine site ligands with functional selectivity for α_2/α_3 -subtypes of human GABA_A receptor-ion channels. *Journal of medicinal chemistry*, 2002. 45(9): p. 1887-1900.
- [33] Abo-Ghalia, M.H., A.E.-G.E. Amr, and M.M.J.Z.f.N.B. Abdalah, Synthesis of some new (N α -dipicolinoyl)-bis-L-leucyl-DL-norvalyl linear tetra and cyclic octa bridged peptides as new antiinflammatory agents. 2003. 58(9): p. 903-910.
- [34] Puerstinger, G., et al., Antiviral 2, 5-disubstituted imidazo [4, 5-c] pyridines: Further optimization of anti-hepatitis C virus activity. 2007. 17(18): p. 5111-5114.
- [35] Amr, A.E.G.E., et al., Synthesis and reactions of some new substituted pyridine and pyrimidine derivatives as analgesic, anticonvulsant and antiparkinsonian agents. 2005. 338(9): p. 433-440.
- [36] Mukai, A., et al., JBIR-54, a new 4-pyridinone derivative isolated from *Penicillium daleae* Zaleski fE50. 2009. 62(12): p. 705-706.
- [37] Mamedov, I., et al., Antibacterial activity of 2-amino-3-cyanopyridine derivatives. 2020. 30(4): p. 498-499.
- [38] Alrobaian, M., et al., An eco-friendly technique: Solvent-free microwave synthesis and docking studies of some new pyridine nucleosides and their pharmacological significance. 2019. 24(10): p. 1969.
- [39] Abdel-Latif, N.A., Synthesis and antidepressant activity of some new coumarin derivatives. *Scientia Pharmaceutica*, 2005. 73(4): p. 193-216.
- [40] Martin, C., et al., Airway relaxant and anti-inflammatory properties of a PDE4 inhibitor with low affinity for the high-affinity rolipram binding site. 2002. 365: p. 284-289.
- [41] Girgis, A.S., et al., Novel synthesis of [1]-benzothiepine [5, 4-b] pyridine-3-carbonitriles and their anti-inflammatory properties. 2007. 15(6): p. 2403-2413.
- [42] Alaa, A.-M., H.I. El-Subbagh, and T. Kunieda, Lewis acid-promoted transformation of 2-alkoxy pyridines into 2-aminopyridines and their antibacterial activity. Part 2: remarkably facile C-N bond formation. *Bioorganic & medicinal chemistry*, 2005. 13(16): p. 4929-4935.
- [43] Faidallah, H.M., et al., Synthesis of Some 1, 4, 6-Trisubstituted-2-oxo-1, 2-dihydropyridine-3-carbonitriles and Their Biological Evaluation as Cytotoxic and Antimicrobial Agents. *Archiv der Pharmazie*, 2015. 348(11): p. 824-834.

International Journal of Novel Research in Life Sciences

 Vol. 12, Issue 2, pp: (1-8), Month: March - April 2025, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

- [44] Attia, A.M., et al., New 2-oxopyridine/2-thiopyridine derivatives tethered to a benzotriazole with cytotoxicity on MCF7 cell lines and with antiviral activities. *Letters in Drug Design & Discovery*, 2020. 17(2): p. 124-137.
- [45] Haggam, R., et al., O-Glycosylation/Alkylation and Antimicrobial Activity of 4, 6-Diaryl-2-Oxonicotinonitrile Derivatives. *Journal of Heterocyclic Chemistry*, 2017. 54(1): p. 375-383.
- [46] Hammam, A.E.G., et al., Chemistry of seven-membered heterocycles, VI. Synthesis of novel bicyclic heterocyclic compounds as potential anticancer and anti-HIV agents. 2000. 55(5): p. 417-424.
- [47] Kumar, S., et al., Antiplasmodial activity of [(aryl) arylsulfanylmethyl] pyridine. 2008. 52(2): p. 705-715.
- [48] Wilson, C.O., et al., Wilson and Gisvold's textbook of organic medicinal and pharmaceutical chemistry/edited by John H. Block, John M. Beale Jr. 11th ed. 2004: Philadelphia: Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.
- [49] Mosti, L., et al., Synthesis and cardiotoxic activity of 2-substituted 5-cyano-1, 6-dihydro-6-oxo-3-pyridinecarboxylic acids and their methyl or ethyl esters. *Farmaco (Societa chimica italiana)*: 1989), 1992. 47(4): p. 427-437.
- [50] Thompson, P., Manganiello V, Degerman E. Re-discovering PDE3 inhibitors—new opportunities for a long neglected target. *Curr Top Med Chem*, 2007. 7: p. 421-436.
- [51] Ismail, M.M., et al., Apoptosis: A target for anticancer therapy with novel cyanopyridines. *Bioorganic Chemistry*, 2020. 94: p. 103481.
- [52] Abadi, A.H., et al., Discovery of colon tumor cell growth inhibitory agents through a combinatorial approach. *European journal of medicinal chemistry*, 2010. 45(1): p. 90-97.
- [53] Kotb, E.R., et al., Synthesis and reactions of some novel nicotinonitrile derivatives for anticancer and antimicrobial evaluation. 2009. 56: p. 908-919.
- [54] Al-Abdullah, E.S.J.M., Synthesis and anticancer activity of some novel tetralin-6-yl-pyrazoline, 2-thioxopyrimidine, 2-oxopyridine, 2-thioxo-pyridine and 2-iminopyridine derivatives. 2011. 16(4): p. 3410-3419.
- [55] Ghosh, P.S., et al., Synthetic strategies and pharmacology of 2-oxo-3-cyanopyridine derivatives: A review. 2014. 6: p. 39-42.
- [56] Mizushige, K., et al., Olprinone: a phosphodiesterase III inhibitor with positive inotropic and vasodilator effects. 2002. 20(3): p. 163-174.
- [57] Abou-Zied, H.A., et al., Discovery of new cyanopyridine/chalcone hybrids as dual inhibitors of EGFR/BRAFV600E with promising antiproliferative properties. 2023. 356(4): p. 2200464.
- [58] Sabour, R., M.F. Harras, and A.B.J.B.C. Mehany, Design, synthesis, cytotoxicity screening and molecular docking of new 3-cyanopyridines as survivin inhibitors and apoptosis inducers. 2020. 94: p. 103358.
- [59] Sabour, R., et al., Discovery of novel 3-cyanopyridines as survivin modulators and apoptosis inducers. 2020. 25(21): p. 4892.
- [60] Fuchigami, T., et al., Synthesis and evaluation of a radioiodinated 4, 6-diaryl-3-cyano-2-pyridinone derivative as a survivin targeting SPECT probe for tumor imaging. 2016. 26(3): p. 999-1004.
- [61] Azzarito, V., et al., Inhibition of α -helix-mediated protein-protein interactions using designed molecules. 2013. 5(3): p. 161-173.
- [62] Sabour, R., M.F. Harras, and A.B. Mehany, Design, synthesis, cytotoxicity screening and molecular docking of new 3-cyanopyridines as survivin inhibitors and apoptosis inducers. *Bioorganic Chemistry*, 2020. 94: p. 103358.
- [63] Karabasanagouda, T., V.A. Adhikari, and G. Parameshwarappa, Synthesis of some biologically active 2, 4'-bipyridine-5-carbonitriles carrying the 4-hydroxyphenylthio moiety. *Journal of the Serbian Chemical Society*, 2009. 74(7): p. 733-743.
- [64] Zoorob, H. and E. Ismail, Synthesis of Pyridone Derivatives MICHAEL Condensation with Ethyl Cyanoacetate, Cyanoacetamide and Acetoacetamide. *Zeitschrift für Naturforschung B*, 1976. 31(12): p. 1680-1684.

- [65] Sakurai, A. and H. Midorikawa, The cyclization of malononitrile and ketones by ammonium acetate. *Bulletin of the Chemical Society of Japan*, 1968. 41(2): p. 430-432.
- [66] M Flefel, E., et al., Synthesis and cytotoxic effect of some novel 1, 2-dihydropyridin-3-carbonitrile and nicotinonitrile derivatives. *Molecules*, 2016. 21(1): p. 30.
- [67] Abdelaziz, M.E., et al., Design, synthesis and docking study of pyridine and thieno [2, 3-b] pyridine derivatives as anticancer PIM-1 kinase inhibitors. *Bioorganic chemistry*, 2018. 80: p. 674-692.
- [68] Zhao, G., et al., Discovery and SAR development of thienopyridones: a class of small molecule AMPK activators. *Bioorganic & medicinal chemistry letters*, 2007. 17(12): p. 3254-3257.
- [69] Mohamed, S.F., et al., Antimicrobial Activities of some Synthesized Pyridines, Oxazines and Thiazoles from 3-Aryl-1-(2-naphthyl) prop-2-en-1-ones. *Scientia pharmaceutica*, 2008. 76(2): p. 279-304.
- [70] Hamdy, N.A., et al., Synthesis, tumor inhibitory and antioxidant activity of new polyfunctionally 2-substituted 5, 6, 7, 8-tetrahydronaphthalene derivatives containing pyridine, thioxopyridine and pyrazolopyridine moieties. *Acta Pol Pharm Drug Res*, 2013. 70: p. 987-1001.
- [71] El-Sayed, H.A., N.H. Ouf, and A.H. Moustafa, An efficient and facile multicomponent synthesis of 4, 6-diarylpyridine derivatives under solvent-free conditions. *Research on Chemical Intermediates*, 2014. 40(1): p. 407-412.
- [72] Hussein, A.H.M., Studies with polyfunctionally substituted heteroaromatics: A facile route for the synthesis of polyfunctionally substituted N-aminopyridines, 1, 2, 4-triazolo [1, 5-a] pyridines and isoquinolines. *Heteroatom chemistry*, 1997. 8(1): p. 1-6.
- [73] Abdel Latif, F., et al., A simple route for the synthesis of pyrano [2, 3-c] pyrazole and pyridine-2-one derivatives. *Pharmazie*, 1993. 48(10): p. 736-738.
- [74] Elmoghayar, M.R.H., et al., Activated nitriles in heterocyclic synthesis. Part III. Synthesis of N-amino-2-pyridone, pyranopyrazole and thiazolopyridine derivatives. *Journal of heterocyclic chemistry*, 1984. 21(6): p. 1885-1887.
- [75] El-Sayed, N.S., et al., Synthesis of 4-aryl-6-indolylpyridine-3-carbonitriles and evaluation of their antiproliferative activity. *Tetrahedron letters*, 2014. 55(6): p. 1154-1158.
- [76] Seifi, M. and H. Sheibani, Studies on condensation of 1, 3-dicarbonyls with malononitrile: Synthesis of 2-pyridinones. *Arabian Journal of Chemistry*, 2017. 10: p. S2453-S2456.
- [77] Salem, M., et al., Overview on the synthetic routes to nicotine nitriles. *Synthetic Communications*, 2018. 48(4): p. 345-374.
- [78] Winter, C.A., E.A. Risley, and G.W. Nuss, Carrageenin-induced edema in hind paw of the rat as an assay for antiinflammatory drugs. *Proceedings of the society for experimental biology and medicine*, 1962. 111(3): p. 544-547.
- [79] Fadaly, W.A., et al., New 1, 2, 4-triazole/pyrazole hybrids linked to oxime moiety as nitric oxide donor celecoxib analogs: Synthesis, cyclooxygenase inhibition anti-inflammatory, ulcerogenicity, anti-proliferative activities, apoptosis, molecular modeling and nitric oxide release studies. 2020. 98: p. 103752.